

Uptake of Long Acting Reversible Contraceptives at a Tertiary Hospital in South-South Nigeria: A 3-Year Review.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Long acting reversible contraceptives (LARC) uptake have not been found to be impressive over the years, despite been a necessary tool in preventing maternal morbidity and mortality.

Aim: The study aimed at determining the uptake of LARC at the Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa (FMCY), sociodemographics, previous contraceptive method used, current choice of LARC, source of information and associations between selected client characteristics and the choice of LARC.

Methodology: This was a descriptive retrospective study of clients who visited the family planning unit of the FMCY, from 1st January, 2018 to 1st January, 2021. A list of clients was obtained from the family planning unit register and case notes were retrieved. For this study, 181 case notes were gotten and data were collected using a proforma. P-value < 0.05 was significant.

Results: A total of 1,281 clients accepted the available family planning methods during the study period. About 14.1% accepted LARC. Majority (32.6%) of the clients were 30 - 34 years of age. Implanon and Jadelle were the commonly used methods (36.6%). Health personnel formed the highest source of LARC information. The reason for the choice of LARC for more than half of the clients was for child spacing (56.9%). There were no significant association between level of education, parity and the choice of contraceptive methods.

Conclusion: The uptake of LARC at the FMCY is low. Injectable contraceptives constituted majority of LARC uptake. Adolescents, the less educated and low parity clients rarely access the family planning clinic.

KEYWORDS: Uptake, Long-acting, reversible, contraceptive

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INTRODUCTION

The average age at first intercourse in women is 16 years and average age of menopause is 51, so most women will need to use contraception for more than 30 years¹. Africa constitutes 16% of the world's 7.7 billion population as of 2019, making it the second largest continent after Asia^{2, 3}. With a population growth rate of about 2.5% which is about five times the developed world, the need for fertility control cannot be overemphasized^{2,3}. Nigeria, like most sub-Saharan African countries has a low life expectancy and high fertility rate⁴. The high fertility rate and low contraceptive uptake in Nigeria has led to a concerted effort to promote the

acceptance of family planning and uptake of contraceptives in the country⁴.

In Nigeria, there is significant unmet need for family planning as 16% of married women have unmet need for family planning while only 15.1% of married women of reproductive age used any contraceptive^{5,6}. Non-usage of contraceptives by reproductive age women who engage in sexual activity could result in unwanted or unplanned pregnancy with its attendant sequelae such as induced and unsafe abortion, post abortal sepsis, ectopic pregnancy and infertility.

Long - acting reversible contraceptive (LARC) methods are defined as modern "methods" that require administering less than once per cycle or month⁷. This includes copper and

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progestogen – only intrauterine devices, and progestogen subdermal implants and injections. Subdermal implants and intrauterine devices which have a half - life of at least three years, have superior efficacy over injections, which require administration every three months. The benefit of LARC is that their effectiveness does not depend on the client's compliance or adherence with prompt return of fertility following removal. Long-acting reversible contraceptives provide effective contraception for an extended period, their 'typical use' failure rates are less than 1% per year, and are about the same as their 'perfect use' failure rates^{8,9}. They are safe, long-acting, reversible, convenient, liked by users, and very effective^{8,9}. They are the ideal contraceptives for the prevention of unintended pregnancies in most women including adolescents. With the availability of family planning methods, the contraceptive prevalence is yet to be increased due to factors inhibiting access and lack of motivation to use contraceptives. The northern part of Nigeria has one of the lowest rates of contraceptive use and second highest maternal mortality burden in the world^{10,11}. This may be due to cultural and traditional beliefs.

Despite very few medical contraindications to LARC use, a variety of barriers at the patient, provider, and systems level have limited access to and uptake of LARCs¹². Efforts to increase access to LARCs can include provision of comprehensive contraceptive counseling on the full range of birth control options (including LARC) for all interested patients, provider training on LARC insertion and removal, and consistent availability of LARCs at local hospitals and clinics. Accessibility of LARCs could also be improved by elimination of medically unnecessary steps between request and insertion, including two visit protocols and STI testing prior to the day of insertion.¹³ The study aimed at determining the uptake of LARC at the Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa (FMCY), sociodemographics, previous contraceptive method used, current choice of LARC, source of information and associations between selected client characteristics and the choice of LARC.

METHODOLOGY

This was a descriptive retrospective study of clients who visited the family planning unit of the Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa over a 3 - year period, from 1st January 2018 to 1st January 2021. It is a tertiary care centre getting referrals from Bayelsa state and some nearby areas of Rivers and Delta states. A list of patients was obtained from the family planning unit register and case notes were retrieved. For this study, 181 case notes were retrieved and data were collected using a proforma. The family planning registers were used to determine the total number of women who opted for family planning during this period. The data were collected over a month period spanning from 8th of March 2021 to 1st of April 2021. Ethical approval was duly given by the ethical committee of the hospital.

DATA ANALYSIS

Data collected were entered in IBM SPSS version 25, analysed, and presented using percentages and graphs. Categorical variable were expressed in frequencies and percentages and presented using tables, and their relationship was assessed using the Chi-squared test. Their level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Sociodemographic characteristics of the clients

A total of 1281 clients accepted the available family planning methods during the study period. One hundred and eighty one clients (14.1%) accepted LARC. The LARC uptake rate was 14.1%. Uptake of LARC was commoner among women aged 30-34 years (32.6%). Ninety-nine clients (54.8%) had secondary education and 170 (93.9%) were Christians. (Table 1)

The acceptance increased as parity increased with a peak at Para 5 and above (33.7%). (Table 1).

Table 1: Socio - demographic characteristics of the clients

PARAMETERS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
AGE (YEARS)		
15-19	1	0.6
20-24	19	10.5
25-29	28	15.5
30-34	59	32.6
35-39	53	29.2
≥40	21	11.6
LEVEL OF EDUCATION		
None	7	3.9
Primary	37	20.4
Secondary	99	54.8
Tertiary	38	20.9
RELIGION		

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Christianity	170	93.9
Islam	2	1.2
Others	9	4.9
PARITY		
0	6	3.3
1	13	7.2
2	16	8.8
3	45	24.9
4	40	22.1
≥5	61	33.7

Contraceptive history of the clients

At least 6 out of 10 clients (60.8%) had not used a contraceptive method prior to use of LARC. In those who had used a prior contraceptive method, the injectables were the most frequently used (36.6%). (Table 2)

Table 2: Contraceptive history

	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
PREVIOUS CONTRACEPTIVE USE		
Yes	71	39.2
No	110	60.8
PREVIOUS METHOD USED		
Injectables		
Pills	26	36.6
Male condoms	1	1.4
IUD	11	15.5
Postinor	2	2.8
Implanon	4	5.6
Jadelle	18	25.4
	9	12.7

As seen in Figure 1; the LARC acceptors opted for Implanon (52.5%), Jadelle (36.5%), and intrauterine contraceptive device (11%).

Fig. 1: Current choice of LARC
Source of information about LARC and the reason(s) for opting for LARC.

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Most (62.9%) of the acceptors got the information on LARC from clinic personnel. The reason for the choice of LARC in more than half (56.9%) of the clients was child spacing. (Table 3)

Table 3: Source of LARC information and reasons for opting for LARC

	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
SOURCE OF INFORMATION		
Clinic personnel		
Outreach personnel	114	62.9
Community health worker	11	6.1
Print media	6	3.3
Friends/relatives	4	2.2
Not stated	26	14.4
	20	11.1
REASONS FOR THE CHOICE OF LARC		
Child spacing		
Completed family size	103	56.9
Prevent pregnancy	72	39.8
	6	3.3

Pattern of uptake between breastfeeding and non-breastfeeding clients

Figure 2 revealed that slightly above half of the clients (51.9%) were breastfeeding.

Figure 2: Pattern of uptake between breastfeeding and non-breastfeeding clients

The association between selected client characteristics and choice of LARC

There were no significant associations between level of education, parity and choice of contraceptive methods. (Tables 4 & 5 respectively)

Table 4: The association between selected client characteristics and choice of LARC
level of education * current choice of LARC Cross tabulation

		current choice of LARC			
		Implanon	IUD	Jadelle	Total
level of education	None	% within level of education		100.0%	100.0%
		% within current choice of LARC		1.4%	0.6%
	not stated	% within level of education		37.5%	62.5%
				62.5%	100.0%

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		% within current choice of 3.5%		7.0%	4.5%
		LARC			
Primary		% within level of education	39.1%	13.0%	47.8%
		% within current choice of 20.9%		27.3%	31.0%
		LARC			
Secondary		% within level of education	52.1%	12.5%	35.4%
		% within current choice of 58.1%		54.5%	47.9%
		LARC			
Tertiary		% within level of education	53.6%	14.3%	32.1%
		% within current choice of 17.4%		18.2%	12.7%
		LARC			
Total		% within level of education	48.0%	12.3%	39.7%
		% within current choice of 100.0%		100.0%	100.0%
		LARC			

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6.730 ^a	8	.566
Likelihood Ratio	7.926	8	.441
N of Valid Cases	181		

a. 7 cells (46.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .12.

Table 5: Parity * current choice of LARC Cross tabulation

		current choice of LARC			
		Implanon	IUD	Jadelle	Total
Parity	>4	% within parity	36.0%	16.0%	48.0%
		% within current choice of LARC	10.5%	18.2%	16.9%
	>4	% within parity	37.9%	10.3%	51.7%
		% within current choice of LARC	12.8%	13.6%	21.1%
1		% within parity	83.3%		16.7%
		% within current choice of LARC	17.4%		4.2%
2		% within parity	39.1%	21.7%	39.1%
		% within current choice of LARC	10.5%	22.7%	12.7%
3		% within parity	54.2%	12.5%	33.3%
		% within current choice of LARC	30.2%	27.3%	22.5%
4		% within parity	44.4%	11.1%	44.4%
		% within current choice of LARC	18.6%	18.2%	22.5%
Total		% within parity	48.0%	12.3%	39.7%
		% within current choice of LARC	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	15.780 ^a	10	.106
Likelihood Ratio	17.522	10	.064

a. 5 cells (27.8%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.21.

DISCUSSION

A total of 1281 clients accepted the available family planning methods of which 181 were LARC giving an uptake of 14.1%, which was extremely low. This rate is higher than 10.6% reported in Nnewi¹⁴, slightly lower than 20.6% in Kenya¹⁵ and extremely lower than 90.2%⁹ and 91.1%¹⁰ respectively in similar studies done in Nigeria. The lower rate observed in this study may be due to poor family planning information on LARC by the public and absence of free family planning services. Over the decades, family planning programs were principally driven by the development partners and non-governmental organizations with external funding^{16,17}. Hence there is a need for government funding and sensitization to improve the uptake of family planning which is key to preventing maternal morbidity and mortality. Uptake of LARC was commoner among women aged 30 - 34 years accounting for 32.6% of the total clients that used LARC for family planning. This is comparable with a similar study done in Abuja¹⁰ and contrast with studies done in Enugu⁹ and Borno¹⁸. Uptake was lowest among ages 15 - 19 years and 20 - 24 years respectively. This indicates that age plays a role in the uptake as older women are adjudged to be able to make informed decision as regards their fertility and are more likely to have attained a desirable family size. It may also be possible that the family planning clinic is not adolescent-friendly, or they are afraid of stigmatization. In this study majority (54.8%) had secondary level of education and the lowest percentage (3.9%) were among those with no formal education and it is in keeping with a similar study in Gambia¹⁸. It establishes that education influences the uptake of modern contraception because of increased awareness and understanding with good access to information.

Most acceptors of LARC were Christians (93.9%) and the least acceptors were Muslims (1.2%). It is similar to a study done by Okafor⁹ and different from a study done by Jumbo et al¹⁰. It may be due to the fact that the place the study was conducted is dominated mainly by Christians. It is also believed that many Islamic faithful confined their wives indoors reducing the chance to access family planning facilities²⁰. Clients with increasing parity were found to accept LARC the most while multipara's least accepted it. This is congruent with other studies in Nigeria^{9,10,19}. It may be due to the LARC methods being considered important alternatives to permanent methods especially in countries with unmet need for contraception.

Majority (60.8%) of the clients in this study had never used any form of contraceptive method prior to the LARC and those who have had, injectables (36.6%) were the most widely used form of contraceptive. This is in keeping with a similar study done by Isa et al¹⁸. This may be due to adequate counselling on the safety, effectiveness and prompt reversal in the clinic. Majority (89%) of the clients in the study chose

implant as a form of LARC of which Implanon was 52.5% and Jadelle 36.5%. Intrauterine device accounted for 11%. This correlates with studies done in Nigeria^{9,10,18} and other studies done in Kenya and Gambia respectively^{14,19}, however contradicts with a study done in Kaduna²¹. This may be due to the minimal side effects experienced and they do not require any action by the user until they need to be renewed. A large population of the study group that accepted LARC got informed by clinic personnel (62.9%) which is consistent with a study done in Gambia¹⁹ and Northern Nigeria²¹. This calls for self-sponsored outreach in churches and women organizations as well as sensitization on social and print media. The study showed that child spacing (59.6%) was the major reason for the choice of LARC followed by completed family size. This agrees with a study by Anyanwu et al¹⁹. There were no significant associations between level of education, parity and choice of contraceptive methods.

CONCLUSION

The uptake rate of LARC among contraceptive seekers in FMCY is low in this study and the preferred LARC was the implants (Implanon). Majority had never used a contraceptive before and the source of information about the contraceptive method was from clinic personnel. There was a low acceptance by those who were younger than 30 years and nulliparous. There were no significant associations between level of education, parity and choice of contraceptive methods.

RECOMMENDATIONS

There is need for a communication strategy that would provide correct information about LARCs safety and effectiveness among women of reproductive age. Adolescents, less educated and low parity clients should be targeted to ensure wider coverage of LARC uptake. There is an urgent need for government support in order to improve family planning and LARC uptake among women of reproductive age. There should be training and retraining of service providers, and consistent supply of LARC should be ensured by the government. Education of the girl child should be strengthened.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Author AG conceptualize the study and wrote the manuscript, Author BAB wrote the proforma. Authors BAB retrieved the folders, Author WS entered it into the proforma. Author PBO, OE, ON proofread the manuscript and made corrections. All authors read and approved the final draft.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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ETHICAL APPROVAL

Ethical approval was obtained from the ethical committee of the Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State.

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